

Gravimetric Determination of Aluminium(III) with 2,6-Pyridinediol

B. K. SINGH, M. P. SHARMA, C. L. JAIN and R. S. SINDHU*

Chemistry Department, Regional College of Education, Bhopal-462 013

Manuscript received 13 December 1993, revised 5 September 1994, accepted 19 October 1994

A number of methods following different techniques, such as spectrophotometry¹, atomic absorption spectrometry², fluorimetry³, gravimetry⁴⁻⁶ are available for the determination of aluminium in its different matrices. However, gravimetric method wherein aluminium is precipitated by ligands^{5,6} has received much attention, as in some cases, it can lead to separation of aluminium from other undesired elements. In the present investigation, the use of 2,6-pyridinediol (PD) as a gravimetric reagent for the determination of aluminium is reported. The procedure has been applied to the determination of aluminium in bauxite collected from Hindustan Aluminium Company Ltd., Renukoot (U.P.).

Results and Discussion

Aluminium content (0.1000, 0.1500 and 0.2000 g) was estimated in solutions of different concentrations. The results show an error of ~0.5%.

A number of diverse ions were examined for their interference in the determination of Al^{III} (0.1 g) by the present procedure. The following foreign ions (I) caused no interference at I : Al^{III} weight ratio : Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ni^{II} ≤ 50; Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} ≤ 20; Cr^{III}, Bi^{III}, Rh^{III} ≤ 5; Ir^{III}, Fe^{III} ≤ 2. Pd^{II}, Cu^{II}, Be^{II} and Hg^{II} interfered seriously and required prior removal.

The proposed method was applied for the estimation of aluminium in bauxite sample. Replicate determinations for same solution concentration of ore were made. The results are given in Table 1. The standard deviation of four determinations is ± 0.50.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF ALUMINIUM IN BAUXITE

Sl no	Determined value % Al ₂ O ₃	Mean value % Al ₂ O ₃	Accepted value* % Al ₂ O ₃	Error %
1	49.21			
2	50.02	49.57	50.12	1.10
3	49.98			
4	49.07			

* Value by complexometric titration

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. Fresh solutions of 2,6-pyridinediol was prepared in hot distilled water. Al^{III} solution was prepared from potash alum and standardised complexometrically with EDTA⁶. Acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer was prepared by dissolving sodium acetate (21.5 g) in distilled water (300 ml) containing glacial acetic (2 ml) and then diluting to 1 dm³. Powdered bauxite sample of known weight was decomposed following standard method and made upto a known volume in acid medium.

Procedure : An aqueous solution of 1% PD containing ten times the concentration of aluminium was added slowly with constant stirring to a warm solution of alum containing 0.1–0.2 g Al at pH 5.5 (adjusted by the buffer). A yellow precipitate was obtained, the solution was boiled, then kept overnight and filtered (Whatman no. 42). It was washed with warm water containing acetate ions. The filter paper was transferred to a silica crucible and the precipitate ignited at 1200°. The residue was weighed as Al₂O₃.

The method was applied for the estimation of Al in bauxite. To the bauxite sample solution (50 ml), 10% NaOH was added to bring the solution near to neutralisation. The solution was further treated with an excess of 10% NaOH (50 ml) and a pinch of Na₂CO₃. The solution was then boiled and filtered. The residue was washed 5–6 times with hot 0.1% Na₂CO₃ solution and the resulting filtrate was acidified with HCl. The determination of Al was then made according to proposed procedure.

References

1. M. TAREK, M. ZAKI and A. M. ELDIRAMONY, *Analyst*, 1988.
2. M. BETTINELLI, U. BARONI, F. FONTANA and P. POISETTI, *Analyst*, 1985, **110**, 19.
3. J. M. EXRICHE and F. HERNANDEZ, *Analyst*, 1985, **110**, 287.
4. G. E. F. LUNDELL and J. I. HOFFMAN, "Outline of Chemical Analysis", Wiley, New York, 1938, pp 55-58; R. A. HUMMEL and E. B. SANDELL, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1952, **7**, 308; M. ASTRUC, "Heavy Metal Hydrolysis Cycle", John Norman Selper, London, 1988, pp. 629-636.
5. C. C. MILLER and R. A. CHALMERS, *Microanal. Silicate Rocks*, 1953, **78** 686; S. L. WILSON and D. W. WILSON, "Comprehensive Analytical Chemistry", Elsevier, New York, 1959, Vol. 1A, pp. 530-534.
6. G. W. C. MILNER and J. L. WOODHEAD, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1955, **12**, 127.